

2016 WORKSHOP REPORT:

Open and Collaborative Science in Development
Network Meeting

Project # 107650-001 (Kenya)

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Executive Summary

This report highlights the main objectives and key outcomes of the Open and Collaborative Science in Development Network first network-wide meeting, held in Bangkok February 17-20, 2016. Workshop participants included project representatives from all twelve of the network's projects, external advisors and the network-coordination team.

Key workshop activities included the drafting of an Open Science Manifesto, the presentation and discussion of twelve concept papers around 'contextual understandings of openness', and a public event to showcase the network and catalyse partnership opportunities in the South East Asia region. Key outcomes included the formation of two strategic working groups that will focus respectively on short and long-term network activities to ensure continued network impact, field building and sustainability.

From a broader perspective, this workshop was of strategic importance in terms of its contribution towards achieving the [larger goals of OCSDNet](#). In particular these included:

Goal 1: Supporting new projects and activities so as to generate evidence on whether, and if so, under what conditions open approaches to science can enable research that contributes to development goals in the global South.

- The workshop enabled valuable discussions around the contextual conditions of 'openness,' and offered speculation around how these conditions may influence research on various aspects of development.

- These discussions have enabled the coordination team to assess and refine our current theoretical framework around how we understand open science and its role in development.

Goal 2: Build a community of Open Science practitioners and leaders in different contexts, by nurturing an interactive research network.

- The workshop was a key opportunity for the development of shared learning and partnership opportunities between diverse and geographically dispersed research teams, which can contribute to network impact and sustainability. Many participants stated that this was one of the most valuable strengths of the event.
- The workshop revealed the important challenges and opportunities of collaboration amongst a highly diverse group of researcher-practitioners.
- The creation of an Action Plan and two working groups will assist in steering network priorities and horizontal decision-making over the next year.

Goal 3: Identify the structural, technical, policy and cultural barriers for individuals and organizations to participate in OCS and determine how these barriers could be addressed.

- New findings on context-sensitive openness highlight the need to address the technical barriers and the unequal distribution of tools and technologies preventing access to knowledge and the realization of the full potential of the open science movement.
- The workshop highlighted the need for the OCS community to develop a ‘common language’ in discussing concepts of science, openness, and development. This vocabulary is being consolidated in the OCSDNet Manifesto.
- Contexts of political unrest, colonial legacies, and community pressures are some of the critical conditions in which OCSDNet projects are operating, hinting at the limitations of current intellectual property frameworks in protecting sensitive knowledge and the challenges of negotiating risks of opening up information concerning oppressed and/or marginalized groups.
- Challenges in collaborative research methods were also identified, including tensions around creating incentive structures for open information and data sharing, measuring and standardizing quality of community gathered data, and navigating relationships between external researchers and community actors. These will be collected as Open Science best practices.

Goal 4: Contribute to the building of a new and vibrant area of study (Open and Collaborative Science in Development), producing knowledge to inform policy and practice, and a community of researchers who identify themselves as working on OCS.

- The development and discussion of a draft Open Science Manifesto during the workshop will be a key tool for policy-making and ensuring network impact. This document also has important implications for ‘unifying’ the network’s diverse ways of working and forms of knowledge.
- The public event allowed for further ‘Open Science’ field building in the South East Asian region, while highlighting the limited ways in which some stakeholders continue to envision ‘scientific research.’
- The network meeting helped to solidify plans for the creation of a shared network publication on contexts of openness, with contributions from all project teams.

I. Background of the Workshop

From February 17-20, OCSDNet members met in Bangkok, Thailand for the first network-wide meeting. The meeting was an important opportunity for project teams, coordinators and advisors to share and discuss the challenges and lessons learned after one year of investigating open and collaborative science around the world. The meeting was also an effort to strengthen the community of open science practitioners and researchers built around OCSDNet and create opportunities for deeper exchanges between members.

Twenty-eight participants attended the workshop, including IDRC's Senior Program Officer, Ellie Osir, four OCSDNet advisors, five members of the coordination team, and representatives of the 12 sub-projects (OCSDNet funded the participation of one participant per project; the rest attended independently). We took the opportunity to introduce our new advisor, Halla Thorsteinsdóttir, to the network, who provided invaluable insight throughout the week. The meeting in Bangkok provided the multiple actors who are part of OCSDNet with an opportunity to share emerging lessons and connect with practitioners from different geographic contexts and academic disciplines.

Logistics and programming were organized by the OCSDNet research and coordination teams, through a transparent and collaborative process. Coordinators met biweekly to outline and discuss the objectives of the meeting and facilitated a consultation process with network members, advisors and partners through monthly reports, interviews and collaborative online documents. The result was a dynamic agenda that emphasized knowledge sharing, research presentations, peer feedback opportunities, small-group discussions and the launch of the network in the South-East Asia

region via a public event.

At present, OCSDNet research teams have recently surpassed the halfway mark in their projects' timelines and the workshop in Bangkok allowed them to meet in person for the first time since the initial research-proposal meeting in Nairobi in October 2014. Unlike in Nairobi, research teams now have a sense of some of the findings, observations and themes emerging from their respective contexts in regards to open and collaborative science in development. The workshop sessions were planned to explore these in more depth.

II. Workshop Activities and Outcomes

The main objectives of the workshop were as follows:

- Check-in with research teams' progress
- Share learnings and challenges
- Obtain feedback on communications and evaluation
- Consolidate emerging research themes
- Expand opportunities for collaboration between research teams
- Review and revise network "outputs" and "outcomes" to date
- Revise and launch a first draft of the network's Open Science Manifesto
- Discuss the future of OCSDNet

Below, we highlight some of the key activities (see supporting material - [Workshop Handouts and Presentations - Shared Folder](#)) and outcomes of the OCSDNet workshop in Bangkok:

1. Development of a consensual first draft of an Open Science Manifesto

Over the past six months, network members have been working on developing a 'Manifesto' that outlines key principles of openness and collaboration in development. The goal of the document is to outline a set of common values around 'open science' and a shared understanding of its

possible impact on scientific research and development.

A member of the OCSDNet Coordination team, Denisse Alborno opened the collaborative working session with a [presentation about the participatory consultation](#) process behind the [OCSDNet Manifesto](#), articulating the feedback loops with which input and learning from the research teams fed into the first draft of the manifesto document. The process started in May 2015, after several members of the network met in Singapore to present at the ICTD Conference. From June 2015, projects' monthly reports, group call, discussions and position papers written by projects were considered part of the data used to construct the Manifesto. Specifically, we looked for keywords, themes and ideas that described the principles guiding the research practice of the 12 research teams.

From the content, we identified three main sections:

- a) Problem: What needs to change in the current traditional and open science models?
- b) Methodology: What research and evaluation methods do we need to conduct OCS?
- c) Principles: How can an OCS approach transform knowledge production?

Based on the data, the main ideas grounding the OCS approach to science were: openness, access, collaboration, inclusion, cognitive justice, development and building a commons. A preliminary draft was built extracting key phrases from the data under each principle before the workshop. The Manifesto session in the Bangkok workshop focused on revising the principles in a **live editing session** of the document by workshop participants. Many points of contention about the tone, language, purpose and content of the document were discussed, and major progress was made in terms of creating a resilient, lasting and impactful document.

This document will be invaluable for field building and policy-making purposes, as well as to ensure long-term network impact. In the next couple of months, ***a working group will be working specifically on finalizing the writing and editing process of the manifesto, and carry it onto its next stage.***

The next steps for the group include:

- Preparing a data inventory to document data sources and collection methods;
- Finalising the document by collaborating with network members;
- Developing a communication and dissemination strategy;
- Organizing a public consultation to foster a larger debate around the principles; and
- Developing strategies for understanding the Manifesto as part of a field-building process.

2. Presentation of concept papers around contextual understandings of ‘openness’ and science

A key activity of the workshop was the [presentation of short papers about context-sensitive openness produced by the research teams](#). Prior to the workshop, each group was asked to write a short (2 page) paper on the context and evidence for their positions. These papers were presented at the workshop and they received peer feedback from other teams and advisors. The information collected during these sessions is of great value for the research team, as we continue to identify the conditions, opportunities and challenges of open science practice. Common themes include:

- Opportunity to strengthen **local and international legal frameworks around openness**
- Opportunity to strengthen **governance mechanisms** for open knowledge management
- Opportunity to make visible scientific thinking and practice emerging in the Global South
- **Challenges in collaboration** between institutional, academic and community stakeholders
- Challenges of developing **intellectual property frameworks** to protect sensitive knowledge
- Need to **define restrictions and limitations for openness**
- Need for a **common vocabulary** to refer to open science principles
- Need for mechanisms for **quality assurance in citizen science**

Presentations also showcased the various frameworks, methods and workshops that project teams are developing to assess the impact of their work and disseminate open science practices further in their communities. These include:

- a) Analytical frameworks to measure degrees and indicators of openness
- b) Community based, participatory research methods to implement open science practices

- c) Advocacy documents to influence policy and decision making
- d) Brokering mechanisms to connect and mobilize key knowledge actors
- e) Pedagogical tools and curriculum for teaching open science
- f) Practical workshop material and tools for open science capacity building

A working group was created to drive the process of developing these concept papers into a collective publication, highlighting the global cultural contexts around openness, as well as evidence based analyses of the impact of open science in development.

Through a post-workshop evaluation, we learned that many participants valued the opportunity to create these papers and receive relevant feedback from peers and advisors:

“I developed a much deeper understanding of the key emerging themes in openness - this helps me to reflect back on my own project and its findings with these in mind, to see how I may reconsider my own findings - were there elements I missed? Do I need to re-think my approach? etc.”

Our next steps in this area include:

- Publishing blogs to summarise key research themes and initial project findings that have emerged during the Bangkok workshop.
- Organizing internal and public webinars led by network members about the tools, workshops and theories they are developing through their research.
- Producing a collective publication on context-sensitive openness.
- Identifying opportunities for a special-issue of an Open Access journal.

3. Launch of the OCSDNet Manifesto through the hosting of a public event

In collaboration with Thailand's National Innovation Agency (NIA), OCSDNet hosted a public symposium at C-asean where Ellie Osir (IDRC) introduced the network, followed by OCSDNet advisor, Apiwat Ratanawaraha. Primary Research Investigator, Leslie Chan, provided a [contextual overview of open science](#) and why it has justified the creation of the network, followed by a panel discussion that included three OCSDNet research teams. Discussion with the audience was facilitated by OCSDNet advisor, Cameron Neylon, and network members engaged with practitioners and professionals working in public policy, social entrepreneurship and alternative energy sectors.

The event attracted a diverse audience of approximately 30 - 40 people. During the reception, all research teams presented their projects via [individualized posters](#) to those interested. As the concept of 'open science' is still relatively new, **this event highlighted for us both the importance and challenge of ensuring the network is involved in critical field building.** Many of the event attendees had never heard of 'open science' previously, but were drawn by its connections with 'inclusive innovation'. Discussing and framing 'openness' in the context of innovation and learning, which are much more widely understood concepts, is an opportunity we will explore in future public engagements. In addition, the concept of "design thinking" and its connections with open science principles was highlighted by several audience members. This led the coordination team towards considering the various disciplinary areas of overlap that exist in science and development research. Indeed, open science, participatory development, design thinking and various aspects of urban planning all have similar ways of working, and it is important for us to share

learnings across diverse, but overlapping disciplines to strengthen best practices and avoid ‘reinventing the wheel.’

4. Collected feedback to improve our internal and external communication and evaluation method

Since one of the network’s evaluation goals is to foster an environment of reflexive learning, openness and accountability, the coordination team is consistently working to gather feedback regarding how we can better support projects and improve tools and methods for communication and evaluation.

During the workshop, another member of the Coordination team, Becky Hillyer [presented an overview of the current evaluation and communication strategy](#) for the network, as developed in partnership with “*Developing Evaluation and Communication Capacity in Information Society Research*” (DECI, a project of IDRC). At this session, we asked all participants to respond to three questions:

- 1) How could the network improve methods of evaluation?
- 2) In what ways could the network improve internal communication?
- 3) In what ways could the network improve external communication?

We received a number of responses that we have now implemented within our action plan for the next year - including the development of online peer-learning seminars hosted by research teams, the development of a specific communication plan for the manifesto, continued usage of peer-learning formats for shared publications, etc. We also confirmed the utility of current tools used in network communications - such as Google Groups for easy communication with all network members, a monthly newsletter (via MailChimp) providing a summary of useful resources/events/blogs, etc.

5. Discussions around longer-term network sustainability

While recognising the challenges of maintaining a large, geographically dispersed research network long-term, the majority of OCSDNet members feel that the value of this

collaboration should not fade away after the two-year project timeline. In the initial planning for the Bangkok workshop, we had reserved the entirety of the final afternoon for discussions around ‘sustainability of the network,’ which the coordination team planned to facilitate through ‘institutional mapping’ and ‘scenario building’ activities. However, that time was used for an discussion around what the future could look like for OCSDNet.

Currently, there are two main intentions among network members; one being a network-based engagement focused on knowledge exchange and partnership building, and the second being a long-term engagement interested in building on the research produced to date and move on to applied research projects that take open science into the policy advocacy, education and environmental sustainability spaces.

These discussions will be a recurring theme within the network over the coming months. In particular, ***a working group was formed to work on ‘long-term impact and sustainability’ of the network.***

Our next steps in this area include:

- Identifying shared interest in network collaboration for future funding proposals
- Identifying medium-term and long-term future funding and partnerships opportunities

III. Lessons Learned and Best Practices

1. Consider the dynamic and collaborative nature of activities when planning workshop logistics

Many of the planned workshop activities did not reach their full potential due to logistical constraints including inadequate room sizes for breakout groups, rushed lunch and tea breaks and an unreliable wi-fi connection. The coordination and on-site team were extremely diligent in accommodating our group, yet the facilities were not fully conducive for the relaxed, dynamic and collaborative spirit we sought to create during the meeting.

Thus, a key learning for us in future OCSDNet workshops will be ***to ensure we have access to large rooms that allow for increased mobility and diverse forms of participation.*** Moreover, a reliable internet connection is key for maximising shared-note taking opportunities, which are particularly useful for participants who do not speak english as a first language. Shared note taking also allows the group to feel that they are contributing towards the creation of something collectively, from the very beginning of the workshop.

2. Consult and incorporate the agendas, priorities and expectations of event attendees into the agenda

Although we requested network members to provide input and suggestions regarding the workshop agenda in advance of the event, we did not provide clear opportunities for all event attendees (including OCSDNet coordinators, IDRC representatives, research teams and the advisors) to clearly articulate their respective priorities for their time in Bangkok at the beginning of the workshop.

As a result, the workshop priorities assumed by the coordination team did not fully correlate with some of the attendees' expectations. ***In future, it will be important to allow everyone, on the first day of the workshop, to clearly define what their hopes and expectations are for the meeting, and create a flexible and adaptive agenda which takes these needs and priorities into consideration.***

3. Create opportunities to build trust and relationships among workshop participants

Although some research team members met during the first network workshop in Nairobi in 2014 and others have participated in collaborative workshops held regionally, several participants met for the first time in Bangkok and had not been regularly involved in network communications over the past year. This is something that we had not thoroughly anticipated, and we intentionally kept ice-breaker sessions to a minimum, in order to allow groups to work more constructively together.

However, as OCSDNet advisor Hebe aptly noted, many important workshop connections develop during informal conversations over meals and tea breaks. Many of our breaks were rushed due to our desire to maximize working time, ***but it is important to recognise that creative freedom and networking are essential components in developing trust and cohesion amongst diverse network members.***

On the other hand, others who have been more intricately involved in the network over the past 18 months felt that the style of facilitation and activities were conducive for participation and discussion, in a respectful way:

“The approach really meant people participated fully, and we had very good in-depth discussions - sometimes about difficult issues. The facilitators created a space where we could raise different approaches and ideas, and didn't all need to agree on everything, but there was still a respectful space among participants - this type of environment is crucial for such discussions.”

4. Facilitate activities that are cognisant of diverse working styles and disciplinary backgrounds

One of the strengths and challenges of OCSDNet is the diversity of network members. Research teams consist of natural scientists, social scientists, biologists, legal researchers, educationalists, community-action researchers, health researchers, participation specialists, artists, ‘makers’ and others. This diversity allows for the development of sophisticated and deep research frameworks across disciplines; however, it also increases the opportunity for ideological conflict amongst network members from different disciplines, who are used to different styles of working.

In future, the Coordination Team will work to create a workshop culture that celebrates the cultural and interdisciplinary diversity of our group, through activities that encourage diverse working styles, research paradigm and productive discussion.

IV. Action Plan

Action Item	Timeline
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<p>Manifesto</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Finalise draft amongst network members 2) Develop strategies for stakeholder engagement/consultation 3) Disseminate and communicate final manifesto to relevant audiences (policy makers, universities, researchers, etc.) 	<p>April 7, 2016 - May 31, 2016</p> <p>May 31, 2016 - August 30, 2016</p> <p>Aug 30, 2016 - February 2017</p>
<p>Publications</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collective, project-level publication on contextual openness 2) Identify opportunities for special-issue journal article 3) Create sustainable intra-network peer review system for all publications 4) Prepare Op-eds about current events 5) Target relevant media outlets for short publications (Sci-Dev Net) 6) Continue regular blog outputs on OCSDNet website 7) Network-level academic publications around larger, thematic issues 	<p>First draft: December 31, 2016</p> <p>September 30, 2016</p> <p>May 1, 2016</p> <p>Ongoing</p> <p>Two published by February 2017</p> <p>Bi-weekly, ongoing</p> <p>2 articles by February 2017</p>
<p>Online Presence</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Update all project web pages on OCSDNet website with emerging findings 2) Develop strategy for internal peer-learning sessions 3) Strategies for online public engagement (webinars, etc.) 	<p>May 2016</p> <p>May 2016</p> <p>TBD</p>

<p>Network Sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Develop strategies for understanding and documenting field building process 2) Identify shared interest in continued network collaboration for future funding proposals 3) Identify future funding and partnerships opportunities 	<p>December 2016</p> <p>Ongoing</p> <p>Ongoing</p>
<p>Areas of Exploration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Development of pedagogical tools around openness / case studies from the network (ex: MOOC) 	<p>TBD</p>